

ПОЭТИЧЕСКОЕ МАСТЕРСТВО АЙДЫН ХОДЖИЕВОЙ

Asatjanova Iroda Qizi

Student of the Faculty of Philology of Urganch State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6815247>

Аннотация. В данной статье показаны уникальные черты поэзии Народного поэта Узбекистана Айдын Ходжиевой, мастерство использования слова, дух лирического героя. Будут проанализированы стихи поэтессы в книге «Вечерние лучи».

Ключевые слова: интерпретация, анализ, оценка, лирический герой, художественный образ, образ, художественные детали.

THE POETIC SKILL OF AYDIN KHODJIEVA

Abstract. This article shows the unique features of the poetry of the People's Poet of Uzbekistan Aydin Khodjiev, the skill of using words, and the spirit of the lyrical hero. Poems of the poetess in the book "Evening rays" will be analyzed.

Key words: interpretation, analysis, evaluation, lyrical hero, artistic image, image, artistic details.

INTRODUCTION

The original poem discovers and enriches the pure definition of poetry. A reader needs dozens of different eyes to see, recognize, understand, distinguish, compare, and contrast a poem. Thirty years ago, I was surprised to see a work of one of our talented avant-garde artists depicting more than ten eyes on the body. A poet who has now entered the poetry world lacks a natural eye. Different eyes are needed to understand, understand and compare the poet behind the poem. The poem also describes the signs of space, the complexities of chaos, and subtle vibrations in the spirit of the "living planet". For interpretation, analysis, evaluation, sorting, messengers of the mind - many eyes are needed.

Comparison, seeing and describing an image that no one has used are important tests of poetry. In Uzbek poetry, there are many poets with delicate taste and unique vision. One of them is Aydin Khodjiev, a talented representative of modern Uzbek poetry. "He brought Bukhara breath to modern Uzbek poetry - his poems, like the lyrics of other poets, are dedicated to people, human pains and joys, sorrows, and he is also a person of the human psyche and, first of all, of the people who lived in the middle of the 20th century. "paints the mental landscapes of a Uzbek woman"

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Until now, Aydin Khodjiev has written "Shabnam" ("Dew"), "Manzillar"("Goals"), "Men sevgan qo'shiq" ("My favorite song"), "Zarkokil qiz va quyosh" ("A girl with a dice and the sun"), "Orzu guli" ("Dream flower"), "Navo" ("Melody"), "Tarovat" ("Refreshment"), "Dostonlar" ("Epics"), "Tamal toshi" ("The foundation stone"), "Mushfiq onajon" ("Kind mother"). For half a century, he has not taken a pen from his hand: he writes articles, creates poetic and prose works, sorts hundreds of manuscripts as the chief editor, and works in "Saodat" ("Happiness") and "Gulchehralar" ("Wreaths") The poetess is an indefatigable publicist: she participates in literary meetings, participates in the events of the Writers' Union. The country wanders. He sees the results of independence with his own eyes and talks with his contemporaries.

The selection of the poet "Evening rays" is a book of life, a delicate portrait of hundreds of destinies, the world of tones, colors, the manifestation of near and far events in the form of poetry, Independence, perspective, the victims of the Shura era. is a long book.

The poet describes the condition of people and the appearance of the stormy land by finding and simulating. "Weeping and crying, the springs became deaf", "Blooming and blooming, the flower beds became barren", "The shores read the letter of Hijran" (p. 251). A blind spring, a barren flowerbed, a shore without water...

In the poetry of wisdom, attention is always paid to time, time, moment, opportunity. Time is a big concept. It spans billions of years. It has special terms, the range from ... to The poetess adds her share of wisdom poetry:

*Opportunity is a golden call,
Grandmother of the time is spinning
Millennium Point
On a spinning wheel.*

The word "grandmother" specifies the time, the occasion. The eternal process of movement is reflected in the chirping and hurchus. Grandmother of time never abandons concepts related to movement (scream, hurchu, eshmak). "Golden", "point", "thousand years" are the stops of time. Aydin writes:

*The heart leaves the place where the girl fell,
The mother tongue lies in the cradle,
And the bulwark of trust - a good address remains,
Lover is a Jerusalem for a blue-eyed girl...*

A woman's psyche is inextricably linked with national uniqueness. The poet deliberately emphasized the name of holy Jerusalem. Jerusalem is a place where many prophets lived and found an eternal abode. Religions and religious views are intertwined here. Most of the lyrical characters in the "Evening rays" selection lived during the rule of the Shura for almost half a century. The pain of humiliation, worthlessness, and dependence gradually turned the bones of the people white. The feeling of patriotism in the homeland was eating a person from the inside. Honorable figures of El - artists, figures, scientists, were banished to places covered with permafrost:

*A time with blind eyes,
A deaf age
He asked for a sacrifice
Red Dragon Age...*

"Thanks to the service of a true poet, we often start to see many things and events that are obvious in life, that we have encountered before. They fascinate us with a new, authentic charm." There are many poems in the work of the poet that flashed like lightning, roared like thunder, and overflowed like a torrent. When reading them, the poet feels from his heart the anguish and conflicts in the psyche of the lyrical hero, fire flashes in his eyes:

*Why between the scissors
Still my soul?
He is in agony
My bones are shaking.*

*My ears are deaf, my eyes are blind
I can't be sick
I saw, if a beshuur,
I'm sleepless and sick.*

In the poem, the complexity of the human mental state is reflected with a skill that is not visible from the outside. "Poetry is not at the discretion of a person. Creativity is the need to free oneself from the pain that has filled one's existence for so long, to be free."

In the poem, the poetess either saves her soul from endless pain by writing what is in her heart as it is in her heart, or drowns in the sea of artistry consisting of the blood of the heart. The poetess is doomed to go to destruction just as she won the victory. Our poet chose such a fate involuntarily.

*Why, honestly, bot-bot
Does my tongue burn, does my hand burn?
Sometimes I am naive and illiterate
Hitting the grass and burning my hand?*

Most lyrical hero of Aydin Khodjievais a woman. A woman is a pillar of life; perpetuates traditions; he encourages his son to be like Alpomish as soon as possible; protects his family and country from calamities. A nation with many brave and intelligent women will always grow and mature:

*The mountains learn
Silence from you
Learn to endure
Your compatriots will turn
Blue from your prayer,
Your curse cracks the stone.
You are the soul of the nation
You are a symbol of the country.
You are the eternal light of the country
Eve - You are a woman..*

According to the poetess, the female being is the origin and original source of three elements (human, people, animal). A woman cannot be described in words. But woman and beauty are twin concepts. One requires the other:

*In the tender hands of a girl
The flower laughs.
In the emoticons on his face
Shula gives two sets of light.
Let the sky be a clear mirror
Waiting for a girl in the hallway
Makes the world drunk*

"Evening rays" is a collection of melodies. The melody is full of meaning, mood, and the spirit of the poet. Melody is a letter of recommendation of the poem. Tone also determines content. More precisely, the meaning is looking for the melody.

RESULTS

Independence is the main theme of Aydin's work of the last twenty years. I think the title of his selection of "Evening rays" is "Inspirations of Independence". The poet's epics and odes are mainly about those who gave their lives and fought for independence. The author looks at the long history of these days. The idea of independence was always at the denominator of the work of our great grandfathers, talented poets and scientists. The poetess begins the epic "Ziyorat" ("Pilgrimage") with an incident in her family. His brother Ne'matjon went to war. The mother spent forty years looking for a sign from her son. The father became weak, the pain knocked him down. Brother did not return. The mother could not mourn her missing son, she could not express her sorrows. All women, especially Nematjon's mother, are reflected in the Mourning Mother in Independence Square. "Flames of free speech" is the cry of the poet's soul, the thoughts that need to be expressed. It contains a lot of biographical images and situations. "Ode to Independence" is a poetic look at the traveled path. An expression of respect to those who served independence. A poetic description of the ups and downs, struggles and losses, joys and worries of the road. "Evening rays" is a collection of selected poems. It is permissible to study them delicately and carefully, to evaluate the applied arts, to measure the vitality and ontological essence of new words, symbolic phrases, and ontological essence on the scales of the soul. In other words, a poet must have different, diamond laser eyes. How would it be if we looked at "Evening rays" with the eyes and taste of a modern poet? In modern works, it is not visible, it is sudur; a very responsible approach to covering the topic is noticeable. It is not acceptable to name the heroes in them, to count them without melting. A name is just a special sign. But it's another thing to list names with a character. A small symbol is a word like a small diamond, agate, or a piece of gold. In his humorous and light poem "2003 snow letter", Aydin Khodjiev created a wonderful image by describing Gulchehra "with a pen in one hand, a child in the other, with the word 'yor-yor' on his tongue".

DISCUSSION

Aydin Khodjiev is a poetess who understands and comprehends this world and its secrets, writes down the happy and unhappy moments of the world, describes the innermost feelings of the hero with the most beautiful expressions. The author has his own words, his own style of writing, and his own theme in modern Uzbek literature. As the folk poet Uygun said: "I can see the breath of poetry in this little girl from this raisin. "If he educates her, she will become a poet." Indeed, it seems that Aydin Khojiev's poetry is focused on the part of women, on illuminating the life of society. Great teachers helped the poetess enter the field of poetry. For example, the poet writes in her "Memories": "Gulkhan" journal took me back to my childhood. 21 years of my life were spent in connection with "Saodat". I owe a lifetime to my beloved teacher Zulfiyakhanim, Shuhrat, teacher Mirtemir, Tokhtasin Jalolov, a wise scientist, Uygun, Toshpolat Hamid, who did not spare me their love, work, and support.

Our independent consciousness is a long-lived concept that penetrates deep into our souls. I am sure that Aydin Hajiyeva will gradually describe Independence as the result of a renewed worldview in clear colors, clean tones, perfect, beautiful, and eternally alive.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, Aydin Khodjiev described the poet's figure, which is sealed for eternity, with such great depth that the reader wants to read Aydin Khodjiev's work again and again, to give his heart to her poems, to make her heart even more. She doesn't even notice. "Evening rays" is a

selection of the talented poetess's original songs, odes, eloquences, and works that lead the poet to think and into the world of sweet suffering. Aydin, a current student who is a poet, is used to the unique and sincere voice of the poetess. May this bright, lively voice be heard for a long time. The study of Aydin Khodjieva's work, and the study of women's work in general, rose to the leading stage in our literature at the beginning of the 20th century. The work of the poetess is important and significant in today's Uzbek literature.

REFERENCES

1. Ozod Sharafiddinov. The happiness of realizing creativity. - T.: "Sharq", 2004.
2. Khodjieva Aydin. Evening rays. Poems, epics - T.: "East": 2010.
3. Abdugafur Rasulov. Criticism, interpretation, assessment. - T.: "Science" publishing house, 2006.
4. Kozoqboy Yoldoshev "The burning word". "Generation of the New Century", 2006.
5. Khodjieva Aydin. Femininity. Poems, epics, odes - T.: "East": 2017